

Exposure to Fake News and its Influence on Voters' Decision: A Study of the 2023 Nigeria's Presidential Elections

By

Adeyanju Apejoye PhD

Department of Mass Communication

Plateau State University, Bokokos, Nigeria

Email: adeyanjuapejoye@plasu.edu.ng

ORCID no: 0000-0002-7187-7403

Abstract

The pervasiveness of online news media within human communication and the relative ease at which information is gathered, processed and disseminated has raised concerns about the truthfulness and objectivity of news reports and how such information shapes a democratic process. This study focused on exposure to fake news by voters and its influence on their voting decisions in Nigeria's 2023 presidential elections. The paper relied on agenda-setting theory as the theoretical lens for investigating the research problem. The study adopted the survey method using voters from the North Central Geopolitical zone of Nigeria who are of voting age of 18 years or older as the study population. Using the Cochran formula to determine the sample size, the researcher drew 384 respondents for the study, and data collected were analysed using frequency distribution and percentage, the results were presented using tables. Findings showed that a significant number of voters shared fake news during the electioneering period, and the ability of voters to recognise fake news online is low. Also, religion and ethnicity are the key drivers for spreading fake news during elections.

Keywords: fake news, online news media, partisanship, election, Nigeria

Introduction

The relationship between online media platforms, misinformation, and how it influences voters' voting decisions has attracted increased academic scrutiny in Nigeria. Scholars and stakeholders have raised concerns about media influence on voters during elections in Nigeria, following the increasing influence of platforms within the online media ecology (Apuke & Omar, 2020; Morah & Nwafor, 2024). Although online platforms have become veritable tools for promoting and projecting political candidates for acceptance by the electorates, the tools for executing this have profoundly contained information aimed at mudslinging, image and profile smearing, fake news, and public deliberation. Initially, the proliferation of online news media and social media platforms on the internet, particularly its ability to facilitate diversity and plurality of opinion, could encourage a situation where readers or audiences that share the same opinion on issues converge under a platform and insulate themselves from a contrary view, which can result in an echo chamber (Sustein, 2017).

This practice portends danger to the democratic system. It can significantly distort and affect the choice of candidates and, by extension, destabilise society by promoting ideological, religious, and ethnic divides on digital platforms, which are drawbacks to Nigeria's unity and progress. The Federal Minister of Information in Nigeria, for instance, during the 2019 general elections, argues that the biggest threat to the 2019 general election in Nigeria was fake news and hate speech (Lai Mohammed, 2018). This paper focuses on fake news on online media platforms and how it influences and affects voters' decisions on how they vote, with a focus on Nigeria's North Central geopolitical zone as the study area. As a result, the researcher raised an overarching research question:

RQ: How does voter exposure to fake news on online media platforms influence their voting decisions?

The Internet, Fake News, Elections and Voting Pattern

The internet undoubtedly remains one of the technological innovations in human history that has revolutionised the information and communication sphere and affects every field of human endeavours. The belief is that the total number of people connected to the internet is far more than the population of a single society (Kumar, 2016). The internet can make people better

informed about politics, democratise news, give more power to the citizens and increase their participation in governance (Gillmor, 2004; Hindman, 2009). In the same way, the platform the internet facilitates, especially new and social media, has revolutionised and changed the entire information processing and dissemination landscape. As a result, significant innovations exist in how political candidates are packaged and presented, especially on digital media platforms. These innovations sometimes come with subliminal misinformation aimed at influencing voters; intentions during elections.

The new media come with a new centre of power that challenges and creates tensions within the existing power structure. It also deflates the formation of opinion leaders or mediating forces within the communication chain known for distorting the original message to meet their intentions (Curran, 2014). However, the pervasiveness of the internet, especially social media within the sphere of human communication and its affordances, such as the relative ease of information gathering, processing, and dissemination, has raised concerns about the accuracy and objectivity of information and how it shapes a democratic process (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017; Jang & Kim, 2018). Similarly, the online media space has proliferated several information dissemination platforms, and determining the accuracy and credibility of information is gradually becoming difficult (Shellenbarger, 2016). Nigeria is the biggest democracy in Africa, owing to its population size, recently estimated by the National Population Commission (NPC) to be 229.5 million (NPC, 2024). As a result, elections in Nigeria, the most populous black nation in the world, are of significant interest to various stakeholders, including state and non-state actors on the global stage (Cheeseman, 2018), cited in Cohen & Nkululeko, 2019), argues that the significance of the Nigerian elections for Africa is tremendous. A flawed election and the political instability that this could generate would not only undermine confidence in the feasibility of democracy in one of Africa's most important states but also slow economic growth in West Africa and the wider region.

For a democracy to be functional and inclusive and serve its primary role in a society, it requires the participation of the citizenry's public deliberation on matters of public discourse. Therefore, citizens must be adequately informed, and this helps to sustain the functionality of a democratic system (Lewandowsky et al., 2017). However, the realisation of these expectations is determined

by the type, quality, and authenticity of the information available to the citizens in the opinion-formation process (Tenove et al., 2018). Also, the increasing prominence of the internet and the new media within the political and media landscape, which alter news processing and the production process, the speed of dissemination, access and ownership have become an issue of global concern. At the onset of the internet technology, optimists believed the internet had transformative features such as expanding political participation, enhancing democratic participation, and widening access to knowledge. Similarly, techno-utopians argue that the internet can help democratise news and give more power to the citizens regarding the production and consumption of information (Gillmor, 2004; Hindman, 2009). In the same vein, the embedded algorithms on the various social media platforms have contributed to the prominence of partisan media and polarisation within the online platforms on the one hand (Druckman et al., 2018; Mustafaraj & Metaxas, 2017), and unmoderated news sites that encourage anonymity and incivility within the online space on the other (Mustafaraj & Metaxas, 2017).

A key technique regularly used by political actors in Nigeria in their sublime struggle for power control, primarily during elections, revolves around misinformation and disinformation in the mass media. For instance, the 2019 general elections in Nigeria attracted many malicious and scandalous allegations in the media, especially between the two major parties, the People's Democratic Party (PDP) and the All-Nigeria Congress (APC). Fisher (2019), cited in Reality Check Team (2019), asserts that parties support and encourage the dissemination of divisive "fake news" on their behalf but have little control over its development and spread. At the height of the 2019 electioneering period, political rallies and campaigns in the media, including social media platforms, became awash with misinformation and disinformation, especially on the two leading candidates - Buhari and Atiku - that at a point, the Minister of Information warned of the threat posed by fake news to the society.

Fake news is one factor that has become a tool over time for driving partisanship, sustaining polarisation, and being effective in the mind game for manipulating opinion. Lately, fake news has taken centre stage within politics and the new media ecosystem, becoming a narrative tool for contestation within the political space. Fake news is not a new phenomenon, as it has been within the communicative space long before the Gutenberg printing technology revolution that

gave birth to modern journalism and sometimes takes the shape of propaganda (Floridi, 1996; Ireton & Posetti, 2018). However, the presence of digital media today has increased the speed of its proliferation, and Ireton & Posetti (2018) argue that there has been an increasing weaponisation of information in the 21st century with social media and other digital media platforms being deplored by states, politicians to amplify disinformation and misinformation to uncritical publics.

The 2016 presidential election in the United States of America, especially President Donald Trump's labelling of news reports against his candidacy as false, opened a vista of debates within the global media discursive space on the influence of fake news in elections. Fake news as a construct has been used loosely and is part of common parlance so much that its meaning and contextualisation is floating depending on who is using it and for what motive it is used. Therefore, defining fake news is fuzzy because the term is subjectively used and setting a boundary between what content is factual and what is not may be difficult. For instance, news content may be labelled to as fake news where it does not favour a candidate even though the evidence within the news content can be verified. Also, the United Kingdom's House of Common, Digital, Culture, Media and Sport Committee's fifth report of the session 2017-2019 argues that the arbitrary use of the concept of 'fake news' by some people to describe any information they disagree with has made the term difficult to define, and hence should be discarded for 'misinformation' and 'disinformation' (Committee, 2018). Fake news is intentionally produced to deceive or mislead citizens (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017; Vargo et al., 2018). This definition unpacks what fake news is from an angle of disinformation and fails to acknowledge that fake news can also be unintentional sometimes, which is misinformation and the other side of the fake news coin. Besides, the dissemination of fake news is influenced by the urge to make a financial gain and exert influence within a particular political or economic sphere (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017).

Partisan media is one key factor fuelling fake news (Fourchard, 2011). Partisan media are a type of media that provide information to citizens from a slanted perspective to support their position, belief or ideological standpoint. In other words, partisan media projects a particular political agenda (Levendusky, 2013). Within the online environment, which includes social media and

online news platforms, partisanship has also become an issue in the form of ideological polarisation, and this is made possible by exposing readers to news content that is congruent with their ideological dispositions and blocking those comments that are incongruent with their ideological, political or social leanings. Faris (2017) argues that partisanship in the media is promoted by news outlets that provide the audience with a one-sided view of an event or information. The partisanship resulting from the propagation of fake news is based on religion, ethnicity, and political affiliation, which are technically driven not by party ideologies but by mere party affiliation to struggle for a share of the commonwealth. Before the pervasiveness of online news and the social media platforms within the political space and the election process in Nigeria, the narratives of fake news influenced by partisanship during elections were expressed on legacy media and at political campaign rallies (Popoola, 2012). However, the relative ease with which people access information on the internet, the near absence of news processing mechanisms typical of legacy media before the dissemination of information on the internet, and the availability of deliberative space for citizens, which in some cases has no barrier to participation, has called for a reassessment of the online environment

Theoretical plank

This study adopted the agenda-setting theory as its theoretical framework. The agenda-setting theory was propounded by (Mccombs & Shaw, 1972) to counter the prevailing assumptions about the effect of the mass media that the consumption of media contents produced an immediate impact. Instead, the agenda-setting theory argues that the news media has a noticeable influence on public opinion, and this influence is driven by the level of importance or significance placed on a particular news item about other issues (Guo & Vargo, 2018; McCombs & Shaw, 1993; Shaw et al., 2008; Vargo et al., 2018). This importance is sometimes predicated on the frequency at which news content is repeated. Also, the public's perception of an issue can be influenced by the salience conferred on it by the press. Similarly, agenda-setting theory explains how the mass media select specific issues and repeatedly disseminate stories about the chosen matter to the public, and gradually, because of the prominence and frequency conferred on the topic, it assumes the highest level of importance in audience perception and influences their train of thought. Therefore, Shaw et al. (2008) explain that media mediation over an issue increases knowledge and understanding about it and argue that a relationship exists

between matters that are hyped in the media and how the public perceives such events. Therefore, the central thesis of the earlier work in agenda-setting theory or what is referred to as the 'first level' agenda-setting theory 'tell us what to think about and not what to think' (Guo & Vargo, 2018; McCombs & Shaw, 1972).

Agenda-setting theory has attracted a lot of critical examination and refinement from scholars since its introduction into the ecology of communication study by McCombs and Shaw. In this re-examination of agenda-setting theory, some of the studies focus on studying those responsible for agenda-setting, while others focus on the suitability of the agenda-setting theory to the study of online news media environment (Djerf-Pierre & Shehata, 2017; Shaw et al., 2008; Vargo et al., 2018). However, one of the drawbacks of agenda-setting theory is its focus on the process through which salience is placed on a particular news item and its eventual results, ignoring the complexities involved and thus neglecting the interaction of '... the social agents, the social games and the social structures that shaping them' (Nollet Jérémie, 2011). The agenda-setting theory is 'media-centric' and confers exclusive power on the media in its analysis of factors responsible for determining what the public thinks about at any period. In reality, however, the relationship between the mass media and agents such as political actors and government agencies and how the latter use the media to further the cause of their political interests determines how an agenda is set (Nollet Jérémie, 2011).

The second level of agenda-setting theory attempts to address the interplay of attributes that shape a particular issue and how they influence the setting of public agendas by the mass media. (Guo & Vargo, 2018; Shaw & McCombs, 2008; Vargo & Guo, 2017) At the second level of agenda-setting theory, how an issue is perceived and understood by the public is equally important as the frequency of coverage the news event attracts (Coleman & Banning, 2006; McCombs, 2005). Recent studies have directed attention to how the interaction between the various media plays a role in agenda-setting, referred to as intermedia agenda-setting. Journalists work in clusters while covering news events, and they often compare notes and check the direction taken by more traditional, elite, and popular media. (Vargo & Guo, 2017) argue that journalists are willing to validate and confer credibility on a news story by comparing notes with colleagues, mostly from the most established and big media organisations.

Certain factors sometimes drive the intermedia agenda-setting (IAS), such as the attempts to authenticate a news story, and some of the news organisations, especially those whose popularity, size and credibility cannot be compared to the more established, big news organisations, rely on the latter for validating and conferring authoritativeness on a news item. Economic imperatives such as the need to cut costs, particularly among small media organisations, and to stay afloat in the competitive and proliferated news media market also fuel the intermedia agenda-setting (Harder et al., 2017; Vonbun et al., 2016). Several studies have explained the use of intermedia agenda-setting theory for the study of online news environment and show how the mass media set public agendas online (Harder et al., 2017; Meraz, 2011; Shaw et al., 2008; Vargo & Guo, 2017; Vonbun et al., 2016; (Meraz, 2011) argues that the influence of the elite news organisation will not wane soon but rather continue to grow due to the inherent characteristics of the internet, which harps on the frequency of visitations to the website. Harder et al. (2017) also argue that online media strongly influences other forms of mass media, especially those that do not publish regularly. In this same vein, studies have established a connection between fake news and intermedia agenda-setting, as the homogeneity of contents among the diverse media platforms can fuel the dissemination of fake news, and this could lead to the online news media setting the agenda or the online phoney news site doing the same (Vargo et al., 2018).

Shaw & McCombs (2008) explain the role of agenda-setting theory within the online media ecology from the perspectives of 'civic osmosis' and 'agenda melding'. The 'civic osmosis' view explains that the proliferation and the diversity of the media, especially with social media platforms, have not affected the formation of a public agenda. In terms of agenda melding, as another perspective for the analysis and understanding of setting public agenda online, Shaw and McCombs argue that the acceptance of an agenda by the audience is predicated on their nuances and how they meld the agenda received from the mass media along with their interests. Although the internet and social media did not exist when McCombs and Shaw developed the agenda-setting theory, its tenets are still relevant as guides for investigating news and information within the online environment. Its capacity for conferring salience on issues and intermedia agenda-setting as a later strand of the theory that emphasises how the relationships between various media outlets affect agenda-setting is employed in this study to understand and

provide answers to the research questions raised. Therefore, the intermedia agenda-setting element of agenda-setting theory will be drawn as a framework of analysis to illuminate the Nigerian case under study.

Method

The researcher adopted the online survey research method for the study. The population of study are Nigerians in the North Central geopolitical zones of Nigeria who are 18 years and above, which is the age prescribed by the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria for which to vote and be voted. According to the Independent National Electoral Commission, and based on the 2023 voters register, the total number of voters in the North-Central geopolitical zone is 13,793,424, representing the study population for the research. Due to the methodological choice for the research, which is an online survey, the researcher focused on citizens in the geopolitical zone who could access and use the internet to complete online surveys. The reason for the adoption of the online survey method is that the researcher did not have the funding to collect physical survey data across the six states in the zone: Benue, Plateau, Kwara, Nasarawa, Kogi, and Niger. According to the Cable Index Report (2024), the total number of internet users in the North-Central region of Nigeria is 28.7 million people, including citizens not on the voters' register.

To draw the sample population for the study, the researcher used the Cochran sample size calculation formula, adjusting it to the finite size of the population of the study:

$$n_0 = \frac{Z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1 - p)}{e^2}$$

Therefore, the researcher plugged numbers into the formulas as follows:

Z = 1.96, representing 95% level of confidence

P = 0.5 representing proportion estimate

E = representing the margin of error

Therefore, the calculation is shown below

$$n_0 = \frac{(1.96)^2 \cdot 0.5 \cdot 0.5}{0.05^2} = \frac{3.8416 \cdot 0.25}{0.0025} = \frac{0.9604}{0.0025} = 384.16 \approx 384$$

Subsequently, the researcher adjusted the formula to accommodate a finite population, as shown below:

$$n = \frac{n_0}{1 + \left(\frac{n_0 - 1}{N}\right)} = \frac{384}{1 + \left(\frac{383}{13,793,424}\right)} \approx 384$$

With the calculation, the sample size for the study is 384.

A survey questionnaire link was generated on Google Forms and administered to the sample population by posting survey links on different political WhatsApp groups in the states recommended to the researcher by contacts. The link was also posted on students' social media pages on Facebook and WhatsApp in the various higher institutions in the six states. For the administration of the survey, the study used stratified sampling and proportional allocation to determine the number of respondents in each of the six states/strata in the geopolitical zone. The distribution is as represented in the table below:

Table 1:

Proportional Sample Size for Each Stratum

State/Strata	Population	Proportion%	Sample Size (384 x proportion)
Plateau	2,789,528	20.22	78
Kogi	1,932,654	14.01	54
Nasarawa	1,899,244	13.77	53
Kwara	1,695,927	12.30	47

Benue	2,777,727	20.15	77
Niger	2,698,344	19.57	75
Total	13,793,424	100	384

Data Analysis

Table 2:

States of Respondents and Religious Affiliations (N = 384)

Geopolitical Zones	Christianity (%)	Islam (%)	Traditional Religion (%)	Total Respondents
Benue	69	2	6	77
Kogi	28	26	0	54
Kwara	19	28	0	47
Nasarawa	30	19	4	53
Niger	29	46	0	75
Plateau	67	11	0	78
Total	242	132	10	384

Note:

The analysed data in this table provides background to the sample respondents used for the study by indicating the population's demographic features for the study in terms of religion and geopolitical zones. By implication, the results reflect the dominant religious affiliation patterns across each of the six states in the geopolitical zones.

Table 3

Political Status of Respondents (N = 384)

Status	Frequency	Percent (%)
Voter/non-party member	296	77.08%
Voter/Party member	88	22.92%
Total	384	100%

Note:

The table shows that most respondents are registered voters for elections but are not registered political party members. While 77.08% of the respondents are voters who are not affiliated to any political parties, 22.92% of the respondents are active politicians through their memberships of political parties.

Table 4:

Internet Platforms Preference for accessing political content among respondents (N = 384)

Social Platform	Media	Frequency	Percentage %
X		98	25.52
Online websites	news	89	23.18
Facebook		112	29.17
WhatsApp		56	14.58
Instagram		16	4.17
TikTok		13	3.39
Total		384	100%

Note:

The table indicates that Facebook, X, and online news websites are the three most preferred platforms for citizens to access political content. While respondents also used other platforms like WhatsApp, Instagram and TikTok for accessing political news contents, the three platforms earlier mentioned are more significant in the frequency of usage among citizens.

Table 5
Ability to Identify Fake News Online (N=384)

Category	Frequency	Percentage %
Very Poor	90	23.44
Poor	148	38.54
Neutral	39	10.16
Good	76	19.79
Very Good	31	8.07
Total	384	100%

Note:

The table showed that respondents' abilities to identify fake news/information content online is very low, as 61.98% indicated their levels of fake news awareness are either poor or very poor. The media literacy level is low, with 27.86 affirming their abilities to identify fake news as good or very good and 10.16% neutral about their knowledge of fake books.

Table 6
Exposure to Fake News Online (N=384)

Category	Frequency	Percentage %
Never	25	6.51
Rarely	14	3.65
I do not Know	143	37.24
Often	162	42.19
Very Often	40	10.42
Total	384	100%

Note:

The analysed data in this table showed the respondents' pattern of exposure to fake news online. The analysis indicated that the difference between those aware of their exposure to fake news and those not is not significant. The reason for this is connected to Table 4, which shows that respondents' level of awareness of fake news online is low.

Table 7

Reaction to Fake News After Exposure (N=384)

Category	Frequency	Percentage %
Ignored	83	21.61
Verified	79	20.57
Shared	164	42.71
Flagged/Reported	58	15.10
Total	384	100%

Notes

The above table shows patterns of sample population reactions to fake news after exposure. The analysis showed that the percentage of those who shared fake news content after exposure is higher than any other categories of responses in the table.

Table 8

Factors influencing the sharing of fake news during elections (N=384)

Category	Frequency	Percentage %
Religion	102	21.61
Ethnicity	156	20.57
Political Affiliation	Party 76	42.71
Total	384	100%

Note:

The data analysed in the table emanated from an open-ended question on the factors responsible for spreading fake news during elections, and it is a follow-up to the question and data analysed in Table Six. Religion, ethnicity, and political party affiliation are the key factors responsible for the spread of fake news during presidential elections in Nigeria.

Table 9

Fake news influence on Voters' Decisions (N=384)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage %
Yes		192	25.52
Not		142	23.18
Unsure		11	29.17
Total		384	100%

Note

The table shows respondents' responses to the influence of fake news on voters' decisions concerning voting in the 2023 Presidential elections in Nigeria. The percentage difference between those who believed fake news influenced voters' choices and those who think otherwise is close. While 25.52% believed fake news influences the voters, 23.18% felt otherwise.

Discussion of Findings

This study focuses on fake news online and how it influences voters' decisions in the 2023 presidential elections in Nigeria. It raised one overarching research question with specific objectives and used descriptive method of data analysis using frequency distribution and percentage to analyse the data collected. Research findings tease out some dynamics around online fake news influence on the 2023 presidential elections in Nigeria. Firstly, the findings indicated evidence of fake news influencing voters' decisions in the 2023 presidential elections. Although, the percentage of those who believed there was an influence is lower when compared to those who are unsure, and it is slightly higher than those who did not think there was an influence. Nevertheless, the number of those who believed there was an influence is high enough to be reported as a key finding. This finding is consistent with other studies' findings that exposure to fake news influenced voters' voting decisions (Calvillo et al., 2021; Cantarella et al., 2023; Okpala, 2024).

Another finding from the analysed data showed that citizens' ability to recognise fake news content online is poor. This finding has a related connection with the first finding, as previous

studies have pointed to the fact that poor and low capacity to identify what is fake news online often results in a low level of cognitive reflection about news stories capable of influencing affected citizens beliefs and tendency to share such stories (Calvillo , et al., 2021; Pennycook & Rand, 2019) Tackling this may require some form of information literacy interventions aimed at educating citizens on identifying fake news as doing so is essential to strengthening democracy in political education, socialisation and participation. Increased information literacy activities will enhance citizens' critical abilities to engage with online news content and decipher when information is inaccurate.

Also, the dissemination of fake news is not limited to online news outlets and webpages known for their partisanship, as some legacy news media organisations also joined the fray by disseminating unclarified information about candidates. Some of the fake news that went viral during the electioneering period was also given prominence by the legacy and big media news organisations in the form of news reports, editorials and news commentaries, thus further promoting the issues as a public agenda. For instance, news on the death of President Buhari and his purported cloned replacement was initially reported by Radio Biafra- an online radio station and the legacy media also picked the story, thus placing saliency on the story. Therefore, the attention given to the report by the legacy media confirmed one of the arguments of the intermedia agenda-setting theory that interaction between different media organisations in sourcing for news can have a bearing on agenda-setting (Guo & Vargo, 2018; Meraz, 2011; Shaw & Mccombs, 2008; Vargo et al., 2018)

Findings also identify religion and ethnicity as the key drivers promoting the spread of fake news in Nigeria. Of course, the data collected and analysed around drivers of fake news identified three themes: religion, ethnicity and political/party affiliations. However, religion and ethnicity are the two dominant themes responsible for the spread of fake news during the 2023 presidential elections. These predominant themes, including party affiliations accountable for the circulation of fake news during the 2023 general elections, are like a 'floating signifier' used by supporters to expand political parties and candidates' hegemonic influence on voters. This result is consistent with Farkas and Schou's (2018) findings that fake news has become a tool for criticising, distorting and delegitimising an opposition camp with contrary views. However, this study is

descriptive and has some limitations. The researchers did not employ inferential statistics in the analysis of the data collected, did not raise a hypothesis, and therefore cannot draw conclusions from the results of the data analyses. Also, the study and sample populations are drawn from a specific geopolitical zone of Nigeria, and the results from the study cannot be generalised across the entire country.

Conclusion

The electioneering activities around the 2023 presidential election in Nigeria including media, involved the internet and social media use on a scale never experienced before. This experience came with the circulation of fake news, which this paper focused on. The study concluded that there was noticeable evidence of fake news in the online media ecosystem during the presidential elections, and it influenced some voters on how they decide their voting pattern. The ability to identify fake news in populace studies is still low as religion and ethnicity influence how information is perceived and circulated by citizens on the internet. The scenario will remain so until citizens embrace media literacy training to acquire critical thinking skills that can help them engage with online media platforms.

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